

THE IMPORTANCE OF PHYSICAL EXERCISES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF MASS SPORTS AND THEIR CLASSIFICATION

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Annotation: it is known that physical education has long existed and developed with human life. These physical exercises, in which a person gradually chooses the means for physical education and creates the means of physical education in his life, are hygienic factors, the health-improving forces of upbringing. The physical development of a person is also influenced by various actions. They are used in order to strengthen health, comprehensively and hormonally develop the body, to raise the level of physical improvement of the movement, skills and abilities necessary for life.

Keywords: Physical Education, Physical Exercise, Sports, Physical Culture, mass sports, healthy lifestyle.

ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ФИЗИЧЕСКИХ УПРАЖНЕНИЙ В РАЗВИТИИ МАССОВОГО СПОРТА И ИХ КЛАССИФИКАЦИЯ

Аннотация: известно, что физическое воспитание издавна существовало и развивалось вместе с жизнью человека. Эти физические упражнения, в которых человек постепенно выбирает средства физического воспитания и создает средства физического воспитания в своей жизни, являются гигиеническими факторами, оздоровительными силами воспитания. На физическое развитие человека также влияют различные действия. Их применяют с целью укрепления здоровья, всестороннего и гормонального развития организма, повышения уровня физического совершенствования движений, навыков и умений, необходимых для жизни.

Ключевые слова: физическая культура, физические упражнения, спорт, физическая культура, массовый спорт, здоровый образ жизни.

INTRODUCTION

Through regular physical education and mass sports and the formation of life skills in a healthy lifestyle, it is aimed at ensuring the emergence of a strong immune system against the disease in every citizen, avoiding harmful habits, following the principles of proper nutrition, systematic and effective organization of restoration and rehabilitation activities and mass physical activity activities, creating appropriate infrastructure and other We also need to feel and follow that hygiene also has an important role in the physical education and sports system.

In the formation of such qualities as physical willpower, endurance, striving for victory, dexterity, self-control in students of the higher education system, the importance of physical education lessons and sports clubs is considered high. The reason is the character inherent in the athlete in students, qualities are gradually formed in physical education and sports activities, through circles, and later these qualities become his constant quality. For example, a student whose physical volitional qualities are well formed will also be strong-willed in life activity.

RESEARCH MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

The practical result of physical education in human activity is the degree of perfection of a person's physical fitness and knowledge and skills of movement, high vitality, achievements in the field of sports, mental development. In the formation of the National gene pool, the correct Organization of a healthy lifestyle and the healthy education of the younger generation, physical

education and sports are used as a spiritual and ideological tool [1, 45]. Today we are trying to build a democratic society based on the heritage of ancestors, national values, based on the requirements of our own way of life. It is the healthy human factor that underlies these actions.

Classification is the distribution of physical exercises into groups and subgroups according to their specific signs. Different physical exercises have many similar symptoms. It is important to identify the main character that will allow you to group the exercises. This sign should be of great importance from the pedagogical point of view. Classifications compiled according to various signs many current physical exercises that help to get acquainted with them, choose the necessary ones in accordance with the tasks set, and quickly find the necessary exercises from textbooks and manuals. Especially on the basis of general classifications lies the historically formed system and methods of physical education: Gymnastics, games, sports, tourism. Each of these groups has its own specific significance, and they are further divided into smaller classified groups.

Gymnastics occupies a large place in the system of physical education. It is divided into health-improving, or generalizing (basic, hygienic, athletic) Gymnastics, sports-acrobatics, professional, sports gymnastics, rhythmic gymnastics (and practical) professional-practical, military-practical, sports-practical, development Gymnastics, treatment Gymnastics.

Gymnastics has the following distinctive features: different parts of the torso, some, buttocks and the demand for different aspects and state of their activity influence (muscle relaxation, stretching, etc.): the possibility of distributing physical load: the use of sports equipment and sports facilities: conducting exercises in the accompaniment of music: the variety of exercises. These features of gymnastics make it possible to use it in training sessions with people of all ages, with different health, physical fitness, in order to cope with a wide variety of tasks.

Action games. This is a complex activity consisting of various emotional movements. This activity is carried out in conditions and situations that suddenly change based on established rules. Unlike gymnastics, when performing games, it will be difficult to distribute physical loads.

Action games differ from other physical exercises in the features of the organization and initiation of the activities of squatters. In situations that change suddenly during the game, the need arises to act and stay action tasks in the short term, manifested by physical qualities such as speed, agility. This will depend on the skills of actions. During the game, children's activities are organized on the basis of figurative plot or game tasks, and these are positive emotions for children to perform physical exercises with enthusiasm and in the long term. This in turn enhances their effect on the body, helps to develop endurance.

Sport is characterized by the fact that it is forbidden to achieve a good result in some type of physical exercise, makes high demands on the moral and physical strength of a person. Therefore, it can be applied only at the level of development of the muayam young stage. This requires conditions in accordance with physical fitness [2, 23].

Sport serves to gain physical maturity and helps to educate spiritual and volitional qualities. Therefore, sports squats are especially useful during the formation of a person's organism as well as a person's personality.

The forces of health of nature are carried out in the process of physical education in two directions: physical exercises that organize their routine and are carried out as appropriate conditions (on an open floor, under the influence of sunlight, etc.), that is, natural factors of the environment intensify the effect of physical activity.

Hygienic factors are a prerequisite for the stay of physical education tasks. They increase the effectiveness of the effect of physical exercises on the body of the sufferer. Rooms, physical

education gadgets prevent diseases of the cleanliness of toys, pupils' clothes and shoes. Performing hygienic students gives positive emotions sleep in children and creates favorable conditions for mastering physical exercises. Hygienic factors include personal and public hygiene.

Hygienic factors are of independent importance: they contribute to the normal functioning of all organs and systems. For example: regular and high-quality nutrition has a positive effect on the functioning of the digestive organs and ensures the timely arrival of the necessary nutrients to other organs, helps the child's way to normal development and growth. Proper lighting does not allow eye diseases to occur, creating favorable conditions for students to move. Strict adherence to the daily routine teaches organization, discipline.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Exercise, as a means of physical education, organizes active movement activities of the buttocks. Physical exercises the characteristics of learning and the way to have good results must convey the mind of The Perfectionists. The character of physical exercise mindfulness can be seen in the fall of a number of mental processes. For example: high jump. From the above, the following general conclusion can be deduced. Physical exercises, which are primarily performed, are free movement activities and are used in accordance with the laws of physical education. When said differently, physical exercise is an action that is specially selected and performs educational tasks.

Thus, there will be Haram-harshilik between the conditions taught by life and the tools necessary for the full morphological and functional development of the body. Although all means are involved in the process of physical education, physical exercises have their own morality in upbringing and teaching. The reasons for this are as follows: exercise represents the human system of action in relation to the environment. Physical exercise is a repetition, a return in the field of physical education in the social-historical process. Physical exercises that affect the body of the sufferer, are also ahamiyas in his formation as a person.

The importance of physical exercises in the connection of pedagogic activities lies in the fact that educators are guaranteed physical improvement. Exercise is a tool that satisfies the need for movement of the body. The development of society and physical education, the mutual immortality of physical exercises with Labor and military were lost.

Physical exercises began to be neglected for medical or military work. in the capture of the caravan, the expulsion of the enemy from the natural run or self-desertion from it, short, medium and long-distance running came. They were shot at a similar target and so on. Being in contact with the exercises, the separation now began to prepare people for work and military work, and this ensured them physical and ruqiy development.

The content and form of exercise are maintained in mutual immortality and unity. Dividing physical exercises into categories-some features of exercises in groups that feed them together should be general (or almost General). All the classifications considered were, in fact, applied only to the exercises of gymnastics in different systems and were used in the exercises that were carried out with students at school. They did not cover all the means by which the history of Physical Education decided.

CONCLUSION

There are not enough scientifically based series of physical exercises built up to the pile. In the review of special literature, more and more attention is paid to gymnastics, sports, games and tourism. Diagnosis from it is again divided into groups (Gymnastics is divided into basic and general-type, sports, auxiliary groups for sports). But such a classification is not clear enough, it does not shorten the full mutual combination of the means and techniques of adequate

upbringing. The set of physical exercises, common in the current era and tested in practice, is a separation on the achievements of physical quality and requirements for the performance of additional signs.

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